

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type2_c_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:53:12 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	28.93	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.4415	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_t...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type2_c_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:53:12 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	14.12	μm	
Min:	-7.415	μm	
Max:	6.702	μm	
Size:	319793	digits	
Spacing:	0.04415	nm	
NM-points ratio:	6.556 % (590020 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_ty...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:53:12 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	14.12	μm	
Size:	319793	digits	
Spacing:	0.04415	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	1.211	μm	
Ssk	-0.8883		
Sku	12.49		
Sp	6.694	μm	
Sv	7.423	μm	
Sz	14.12	μm	
Sa	0.6692	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.2459	%	
Smc	0.9678	μm	
Sxp	3.197	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	16.40	μm	
Str	0.7454		
Std	30.50	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.2697		
Sdr	2.850	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.1119	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	1.080	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.1119	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.4593	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	0.8719	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.2077	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:

- ISO 25178 8.
- Furrow 9.
- Texture direction 10.
- Texture isotropy 11.
- SSFA 12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	6.984	µm
Mean depth of furrows	1.147	µm
Mean density of furrows	4101	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	44.97	°
Second direction	26.50	°
Third direction	90.02	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	81.51	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

Information

Method Length-scale (rows)

Parameters

Value	Unit	Comment
*****		Length-scale anisotropy (Sfrac) (1.8 nm, 5°)
*****		Length-scale anisotropy (1.8 nm, 5°)

Information

Method Area-scale (four corners)

Parameters

Value	Unit	Comment
4.363		Fractal complexity
5391970	nm ²	Scale of max complexity
1.403		Heterogeneity of Asfc (3x3)
2.936		Heterogeneity of Asfc (9x9)